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Abstract: More than 11 million ha of olives (*Olea europaea* L.) are currently grown worldwide, 98% of which are localized in the Mediterranean Basin, with olives being one the most important fruit trees in the area. The olive fruit is a very particular drupe since it not may be directly consumed but must instead be processed. Table olives and virgin olive oil are the two main processed products derived from olive fruits. Both are considered staple foods of the Mediterranean Diet and have been produced in the area for centuries, presumably since olive domestication occurred approximately 6.000 years ago. Despite their long history and economic importance, the focus on quality is quite recent. The presence of various and copious amounts of bioactive compounds, some of which are exclusive to olives, is drawing attention to the nutraceutical value of these products. This review aims to integrate the available information regarding the quality of table olives and olive oil with a focus on how preharvest factors may affect quality. The first part of the review describes the main quality attributes considered for each product from different perspectives, including the legal, organoleptic and nutritional points of view, among others. The physiological mechanisms involved in fruit development and ripening, which significantly affect the quality of the fruits, i.e., the raw material for obtaining both products, are also discussed. The review also addresses the potential of both the considerable number of traditional olive cultivars and recent olive breeding programs to obtain products with distinct quality attributes (in terms of sensorial profile and bioactive compounds). Finally, the most recent literature concerning the effect of environmental (soil and climate) and agronomical factors (irrigation, fertilization, canopy management and harvesting) is extensively reviewed.

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1 **QUALITY OF OLIVES: A FOCUS ON AGRICULTURAL PREHARVEST FACTORS**

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15 **ABSTRACT**

16 More than 11 million ha of olives (*Olea europaea* L.) are currently grown worldwide, 98% of which are localized in
17 the Mediterranean Basin, with olives being one the most important fruit trees in the area. The olive fruit is a very
18 particular drupe since it not may be directly consumed but must instead be processed. Table olives and virgin olive oil
19 are the two main processed products derived from olive fruits. Both are considered staple foods of the Mediterranean
20 Diet and have been produced in the area for centuries, presumably since olive domestication occurred approximately
21 6.000 years ago. Despite their long history and economic importance, the focus on quality is quite recent. The presence
22 of various and copious amounts of bioactive compounds, some of which are exclusive to olives, is drawing attention to
23 the nutraceutical value of these products. This review aims to integrate the available information regarding the quality
24 of table olives and olive oil with a focus on how preharvest factors may affect quality. The first part of the review
25 describes the main quality attributes considered for each product from different perspectives, including the legal,
26 organoleptic and nutritional points of view, among others. The physiological mechanisms involved in fruit development
27 and ripening, which significantly affect the quality of the fruits, i.e., the raw material for obtaining both products, are
28 also discussed. The review also addresses the potential of both the considerable number of traditional olive cultivars
29 and recent olive breeding programs to obtain products with distinct quality attributes (in terms of sensorial profile and

30 bioactive compounds). Finally, the most recent literature concerning the effect of environmental (soil and climate) and
31 agronomical factors (irrigation, fertilization, canopy management and harvesting) is extensively reviewed.

32 **Keywords:** Table olives; Olive oil; Organoleptic quality; Nutraceutical quality; Volatile compounds; Phenolic
33 compounds

34 **Abbreviations**

35 DAFB – Days After Full Bloom

36 EEC - European Economic Community

37 EFSA - European Food Safety Authority

38 EVOO - Extra Virgin Olive Oil

39 FA - Free Acidity

40 FAEEs - Fatty Acid Ethyl Esters

41 FATH – Fruit Abscission Threshold

42 FR – Fruit Ripening

43 IOC - International Olive Council

44 LDL - Low-Density Lipoprotein

45 MI – Maturity Index

46 MUFA - Monounsaturated Fatty Acid

47 PL - Phospholipids

48 PUFA - Polyunsaturated Fatty Acid

49 RDI – Regulated Deficit Irrigation

50 VOO - Virgin Olive Oil

51

52 1. INTRODUCTION

53 Olive growing has been traditionally localized in the Mediterranean Basin for thousands
54 of years. According to the International Olive Council (IOC,
55 <http://www.internationaloliveoil.org/>), there are more than 11 million ha of olive trees in
56 more than 47 countries. The majority of this surface (97.9%) is localized in the
57 Mediterranean countries. However, new intensive orchards have been planted in the
58 Mediterranean and in new regions, such as Australia, North and South America, over the
59 last 20 years. The mentioned expansion and intensification of olive growing as well as
60 the perception of olive oil and table olives as healthy foods have largely increased both
61 the production and demand of these products.

62 The olive fruit is a drupe that comprises the exocarp, the fleshy mesocarp (the edible
63 portion) and the stony endocarp. Unlike other well-known drupes (peaches, apricots,
64 cherries, and plums) olive fruit cannot be directly consumed but must instead be
65 processed to eliminate their strong bitter taste, which is caused by the presence of
66 oleuropein, a secoiridoid glucoside (the predominant phenolic compound), in the
67 mesocarp. Other particularities of the olive fruit is its low sugar content (3.5-6%) and the
68 high amount of oil accumulated during maturation (14-30% oil content).

69 Two main products are obtained from olive fruits: virgin olive oil (the juice of the fruit)
70 and table olives; both are staple foods of the Mediterranean Diet. The quality attributes
71 that are considered for each product, including sensory analysis, largely differ from one
72 another; thus, they are addressed separately in the first part of the review.

73 Preharvest factors directly affect the quality of the “fresh” olive fruits, i.e., the raw
74 material for both table olives and olive oil; therefore, the final quality of both products
75 depends largely on the cultivar, ripening stage and management in the field (olive
76 orchards). Similarly, the processing required to obtain both products has an important

77 effect on the final quality of table olives and olive oil. Nevertheless, in this review, only
78 preharvest factors, including the physiology of ripening, genetics, and environmental and
79 agronomic conditions, are discussed.

80 2. OLIVE QUALITY

81 2.1. Table olive quality attributes

82 2.1.1. Definition of table olives and types

83 For commercial trading, olive fruits must conform to obligatory standards that mainly
84 refer to fruit appearance and uniformity in addition to the presence of different defects.
85 Quality standards for table olives were issued by the International Olive Council (IOC,
86 2004). According to this standard, table olives are defined as the product with the
87 following characteristics:

88 *(a) prepared from the sound fruits of varieties of the cultivated olive tree (Olea*
89 *europaea L.) that are chosen for their production of olives whose volume, shape,*
90 *flesh-to-stone ratio, fine flesh, taste, firmness and ease of detachment from the*
91 *stone make them particularly suitable for processing;*

92 *(b) treated to remove its bitterness and preserved by natural fermentation, or by*
93 *heat treatment, with or without the addition of preservatives;*

94 *(c) packed with or without covering liquid.*

95 Table olive processing procedures are intended to remove oleuropein to reduce the
96 bitterness distinctive to the olive fruit. The methods largely differ among the regions,
97 cultivars and ripening stages of the olives. There are, however, according to the standards
98 (IOC, 2004), four main trade preparations: “treated olives” (fruits undergo an alkaline
99 treatment and are placed in a brine, where fermentation occurs), which includes the well-
100 known Spanish-style green olives; “natural olives” (olive fruits are directly placed in a
101 brine), with Greek-style black olives being the most prevalent preparation within the

102 category; “olives darkened by oxidation” (olives are preserved in a brine and darkened
103 by oxidation), which are also known as black ripe olives or Californian-style olives; and
104 “dehydrated and/or shriveled olives” (fruits are preserved in brine or partially dehydrated
105 in dry salt and/or by heating or any other process).

106 |2.1.2. Fruit morphology traits

107 Several traits related to the morphology of the fruit are important for table olives, namely,
108 fruit size, fruit shape and flesh-to-stone ratio (Garrido Fernandez et al., 1997). Olive fruit
109 size is expressed as unitary fruit weight and/or volume, although for commercial size
110 grading, it is calculated as the number of fruits per kilogram. Table olives are preferred
111 to be large (over 5 g per fruit) or medium-size (3 to 5 g per fruit). Nevertheless, many
112 table olive cultivars vary considerably in size (Barranco et al., 2000). Fruit shape is
113 usually measured as the ratio between fruit length and width. Many different shapes may
114 be found among table olives, but spherical rounded shapes are often preferred by
115 consumers and by the industry since pitting them is easier. However, very appreciated
116 table olives such as “Kalamata olives” are notably elliptical and asymmetrical (Tsantili,
117 2014). Having a high flesh-to-stone ratio is essential for table olive acceptance by the
118 consumer. No “legal” minimum value is established, but a 5:1 ratio is acceptable. Stone
119 morphology is also an important trait influencing quality. The surface of the pit should be
120 smooth, and the flesh should be easily detached.

121 |2.1.3. Texture

122 Flesh texture is a quality attribute of great importance for table olives. In fact, “abnormal
123 texture”, based on subjective appreciation, is considered a defect within the quality
124 standard (IOC, 2004), and similarly, kinesthetic sensations (directly related to fruit
125 firmness) have been included in the sensory analysis methodology (IOC, 2011).

126 Nevertheless, no average values are specified, and no correlation with instrumental
127 objective methods has yet been established (Sánchez Gómez and García, 2017).
128 There are no unified standard methodologies to assess the mechanical properties of the
129 olive fruit, although different tests and instruments have been employed for the texture
130 evaluation of table olives. Most methods are based on applying pressure or force to the
131 fruit surface and measuring traits related to fruit consistency, such as fruit deformation
132 (Kilickan and Güner, 2008; Lanza et al., 2010; Mafra et al., 2001), the compression force
133 based on single or continuous measures (Cardoso et al., 2008; Catania et al., 2015), the
134 puncture force required to penetrate the pulp (Cano-Lamadrid et al., 2015; Cardoso et al.,
135 2008; Fadda et al., 2014; Mafra et al., 2001), and the shear force required to break it
136 (Garcia-Garcia et al., 2014; Rejano-Navarro et al., 2008). Instruments for physical
137 measures include pressure testers or durometers, puncture testers or penetrometers and
138 more sophisticated texturometers. Texture is related to the cell structure, the composition
139 of the cell wall, particularly regarding polysaccharides, and the enzymes involved in cell
140 degradation. Thus, indirect methods based on some of these aspects to determine the
141 mechanical properties of the olive drupe have been studied (Fernandez-Bolaños et al.,
142 2001; Mafra et al., 2001; Marsilio et al., 2000).

143 2.1.4. Fruit color

144 Table olive quality also relies on the fruit surface color. Chlorophylls and carotenoids are
145 the main pigments responsible for the color of green olives. Consumers prefer the golden-
146 yellow color characteristic of alkali-treated olives to the brownish colors that natural
147 green olives (non-treated with alkali) usually develop (Ramirez et al., 2015).
148 Anthocyanins are involved in the final color of natural black (Greek-style) olives, whereas
149 the color of black ripe (California-style) olives is achieved by oxidation of hydroxytyrosol
150 (Brenes et al., 1992). The dark color of black olives is one of the attributes that is most

151 valued by consumers, but natural black olives do not usually reach the darkness and
152 homogeneity of black-ripe olives (Romero et al., 2015).

153 For green olives, color determination is based on the measured reflectance at wavelengths
154 of 560, 590 and 635 nm (Sánchez- Gómez et al., 1985). Alternative methods, primarily
155 the CIE (Commission internationale de l'éclairage) L* (lightness), a* (redness) and b*
156 (yellowness) parameters, are currently widely used for color determination for both fresh
157 and processed table olives (Ramirez et al., 2015). In ripe and naturally black olives, the
158 parameters proposed are the reflectance of the olive surface at 700 nm (Garrido Fernandez
159 et al., 1997) in addition to the CIE L*, a* b* color space (Marsilio et al., 1990).

160 |2.1.5. Fruit damage and bruising

161 Fruit appearance is one of the most decisive factors influencing consumer's choice, and
162 a long list of defects affecting olive fruit surface is included within the International Trade
163 Standard for Table Olives (IOC, 2004). Among these defects, bruising is the most
164 common type of mechanical damage, and its occurrence is mainly related to the impacts
165 suffered by the olive fruit during harvesting. Bruising is generally associated with
166 superficial browning (dark spots) on the fruit exterior, but internal damage within the
167 mesocarp, including ruptured cells and a loss of cell wall thickness, has also been reported
168 (Jimenez et al., 2016). Bruising assessment in commercial regulations (IOC, 2004) and,
169 in most studies, is usually limited to a visual evaluation of external damage (Jimenez-
170 Jimenez et al., 2013; Saracoglu et al., 2011). A recent methodology developed by Jiménez
171 et al. (2016) is being employed to assess and quantify internal damage associated with
172 bruising at the tissue level (Casanova et al., 2017; Jiménez et al., 2017)

173 |2.1.6. Chemical composition and nutritional value of table olives

174 Multiple beneficial health effects have been associated with the consumption of table
175 olives (Accardi et al., 2016). The nutraceutical value of this product largely depends on

176 the chemical composition of the fresh olive fruit. However, during table olive processing,
177 many changes in the chemical composition occur, generally resulting in decreased quality
178 parameters, as will be discussed below.

179 The olive fruit mesocarp and exocarp, the edible portion, are mainly composed of water
180 (70-75%) and lipids. The oil content in the olive fruit ranges from 14 to 30%, depending
181 on the cultivar and the ripening stage (Bianchi, 2003). Olives are rich in monounsaturated
182 fatty acids (MUFAs), mainly oleic acid (47-84%) and palmitoleic acid (0.3-3.5%) (Servili
183 et al., 2016). High intakes of oleic acid have been widely documented to be associated
184 with reduced LDL cholesterol (Mattson and Grundy, 1985). Moreover, important
185 amounts of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), linoleic and linolenic acids are present
186 in the olive fruit. Since they are essential acids, i.e., are not synthesized by humans, they
187 should be consumed as part of one's diet (Servili et al., 2016). The fatty acid profile seems
188 to be only slightly affected by table olive processing (Issaoui et al., 2011; Lopez-Lopez
189 et al., 2015), and thus, all of the mentioned benefits remain in the final product. Their
190 stability has been attributed to their insolubility in the processing medium (Bianchi et al,
191 2003).

192 Sugars in the olive fruit represent up to 3.5-6% (Servili et al., 2016), a small amount
193 compared to other drupes. The major sugars in fresh fruits are glucose, fructose, sucrose,
194 and mannitol (Marsilio et al., 2001), although other sugars, such as galactose, mannose,
195 sorbitol, xylose and rhamnose, have been reported (Aktas et al., 2014; Issaoui et al., 2011;
196 Lopez-Lopez et al., 2007). Sugars play an important role in the olive fruit: they are related
197 to the textural properties because they are important components of the cell wall, they are
198 precursors of olive oil biosynthesis, and they provide energy for metabolic changes.
199 During table olive processing, sugars are the main source of carbon for microorganism in

200 fermentation and give rise to the secondary metabolites responsible for the distinctive
201 flavor of the final product.

202 Phenolic compounds are minor constituents of the olive fruit (comprising 1-3% of the
203 fresh pulp weight) but have very important roles in their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory
204 and anticarcinogenic activities (Boskou et al., 2006; Kountouri et al., 2009; Soler-Rivas
205 et al., 2000; Uccella, 2000). They have also been associated with prevention of
206 cardiovascular and degenerative diseases (Bendini et al., 2007). The profile of phenolic
207 compounds in the olive fruits is very complex and depends on factors such as the cultivar,
208 ripening stage or season (see the recent review by Charoenprasert and Mitchell, 2012).
209 The most abundant phenols in fresh olives are oleuropein, demethyloleuropein,
210 hydroxytyrosol and verbascoside (Blekas et al., 2002; Romero et al., 2017; Servili et al.,
211 2016), whereas in processed table olives, almost no oleuropein is found, with
212 hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol being the predominant phenolics (Romero et al., 2004).
213 Indeed, table olive processing dramatically reduces the total amount of phenolic
214 compounds and substantially changes the profile. Nevertheless, there are significant
215 differences among the different processing methods. Generally, the total phenolic
216 contents in natural olives and in green treated olives are greater than those in black-ripe
217 olives (Romero et al., 2004).

218 Fresh olives are rich in triterpenic acids, primarily maslinic and oleanolic acids (1500-
219 3000 mg/kg) (Alexandraki et al., 2014; Medina et al., 2012; Romero et al., 2010), which
220 are mainly concentrated in the skin (Romero et al., 2017). Although there are significant
221 losses during processing, table olives, especially natural black olives, exhibit greater
222 amounts of these compounds than does olive oil. Many health-promoting effects have
223 been described for the olive triterpenic acids, including anti-cancer, anti-oxidant, anti-

224 microbial and anti-hyperglycemic activities (Horiuchi et al., 2007; Juan et al., 2008;
225 Lozano-Mena et al., 2014; Tsai and Yin, 2012).

226 Lately, special attention has been paid to phytoprostane (PhytoPs), a bioactive compound
227 with effects on the regulation of immune function and with anti-inflammatory and
228 apoptosis-inducing activity. It has recently been reported in fresh olives and Spanish-style
229 green olives (Collado-González et al., 2015).

230 The high content of α -tocopherol in table olives (Malheiro et al., 2012; Sakouhi et al.,
231 2008) reinforces the nutritional value of this product because this substance provides
232 protection from free radicals (Cheeseeman and Slater, 1993; Kamal-Eldin and Andersson,
233 1997) and prevents cancer and arteriosclerosis (Armstrong, et al, 1997; Caruso et al.,
234 1997; Nicolaiew et al., 1998).

235 Table olives are not only an important source of bioactive compounds, as described
236 above; since they are fermented products, they are also potential functional foods as
237 carriers of probiotic lactic acid bacteria (Argyri et al., 2013; Peres et al., 2012) and are
238 thus a very interesting alternative to dairy products.

239 | 2.1.7. Organoleptic quality

240 The first standardized Method for Sensory Analysis of Table Olives is quite recent. It was
241 proposed by the International Olive Council in 2008 and revised in 2011 (IOC, 2011).

242 The attributes assessed in this standard are negative, gustatory and kinesthetic sensations.

243 The negative attributes considered are abnormal fermentation, musty, rancid, cooking
244 effect, metallic, earthy and winey–vinegary. Gustatory attributes are salty, bitter and acid.

245 Kinesthetic sensations are related to the texture of the fruit, and the attributes assessed are
246 hardness, fibrousness and crunchiness.

247 Trained panel tasters score the intensity of the mentioned attributes on a scale ranging
248 from 1 (no perception) to 11 (extreme). The trade category quality classification is

249 composed of the categories Extra or Fancy, First, Choice or Select, Second or Standard,
250 and Olives that may not be sold as table olives, depending on the intensity of the defect
251 that is predominantly perceived.

252 This method is being adopted by the table olive industry and by many researchers (Catania
253 et al., 2015; Lanza et al., 2010). Nevertheless, some authors suggest, as an alternative to
254 sensory panels, objective instrumental methodologies, such as the electronic tongue,
255 which has been already used to assess table olive defects (Marx et al., 2017a) and
256 gustatory attributes (Marx et al., 2017b).

257 2.2. Olive oil quality attributes

258 |2.2.1. Legal definition of olive oil

259 According to the European Community (EEC Reg. 2568/91 and EEC Reg. 2015/1830)
260 and the International Olive Council (T.15/NC No 3/Rev. 11, July 2016), olive oil is the
261 natural juice obtained exclusively from the fruits of the olive tree (*Olea europaea* L.),
262 with exclusion of those oils extracted using solvents or via re-esterification processes
263 (European Communities, 2000; European Commission, 2015; IOC, 2016). The IOC
264 classification includes virgin olive oil (VOO), refined olive oil, olive oil and olive pomace
265 oil. *Virgin olive oil is the oil obtained solely by mechanical or other physical means*
266 *without application of thermal conditions that lead to alterations in the oil composition.*
267 *Additionally, any treatment in the extraction protocol other than washing, decantation,*
268 *centrifugation or filtration must be discarded. Virgin olive oil can be split into the*
269 *following three categories that can be consumed directly:*

270 - *Extra virgin olive oil (EVOO), which has a free acidity, expressed as oleic acid,*
271 *of not more than 0.8 grams per 100 grams, and the other characteristics of which*
272 *correspond to those fixed for this category in this standard.*

273 - Virgin olive oil, which has a free acidity, expressed as oleic acid, of not more
274 than 2 grams per 100 grams and the other characteristics of which correspond to those
275 fixed for this category in this standard.

276 - Ordinary virgin olive oil, which has a free acidity, expressed as oleic acid, of
277 not more than 3.3 grams per 100 grams and the other characteristics of which correspond
278 to those fixed for this category in this standard. This designation may only be sold direct
279 to the consumer if permitted in the country of retail sale. If not permitted, the designation
280 of this product shall comply with the legal provisions of the country concerned.

281 Another class of olive oil that can be consumed is refined olive oil. The refined olive oil
282 is the olive oil obtained from low quality virgin olive oils by refining methods which do
283 not lead to alterations in the initial glyceridic structure. It has a free acidity, expressed
284 as oleic acid, of not more than 0.3 grams per 100 grams and its other physico–chemical
285 and organoleptic characteristics correspond to those fixed for this category in this
286 standard. This product may only be sold direct to the consumer if permitted in the country
287 of retail sale.

288 Refined olive oil can be mixed with virgin olive oils for consumption. This category,
289 named olive oil has a free acidity, expressed as oleic acid, of not more than 1 gram per
290 100 grams and its other physico–chemical and organoleptic characteristics correspond
291 to those fixed for this category in this standard.

292 The principal quality criteria for those categories according to the IOC documentation
293 (International Olive Council, 2016) are listed in Table 1. This table only includes those
294 categories that are suitable for consumption. This review is focused on the quality
295 concept, and for this reason, it exclusively considers VOO categories, with a special
296 emphasis on EVOO and VOO.

297

298 Table 1. Principal quality criteria for virgin olive oil categories, refined olive oil and olive oil according to
 299 the IOC documentation (International Olive Council, 2016).

	Extra virgin olive oil	Virgin olive oil	Ordinary virgin olive oil	Refined olive oil	Olive Oil (ROO+VO Os)
1- Organoleptic characteristics					
- odour and taste				acceptable	good
- odour and taste (on a continuous scale):					
- median of defect	Me = 0	0 < Me ≤ 3.5	3.5 < Me ≤ 6.0**		
- median of the fruity attribute	Me > 0	Me > 0			
- color				Light yellow	light, yellow to green
- aspect at 20°C for 24 hours				limpid	limpid
2 - Free acidity					
% m/m expressed in oleic acid	≤ 0.8	≤ 2.0	≤ 3.3	≤ 0.3	≤ 1.0
3 - Peroxide value in milleq. peroxide oxygen per kg/oil	≤ 20	≤ 20	≤ 20	≤ 5	≤ 15
4 - Absorbance in ultra-violet (K _{1cm} ^{1%})					
270 nm (cyclohexane) / 268 nm (iso-octane)	≤ 0.22	≤ 0.25	≤ 0.30	≤ 1.25	≤ 1.15
- ΔK	≤ 0.01	≤ 0.01	≤ 0.01	≤ 0.16	≤ 0.15
- 232 nm*	≤ 2.50**	≤ 2.60**			
5 - Moisture and volatile matter (% m/m)	≤ 0.2	≤ 0.2	≤ 0.2	≤ 0.1	≤ 0.1
6 - Insoluble impurities in light petroleum% m/m	≤ 0.1	≤ 0.1	≤ 0.1	≤ 0.05	≤ 0.05
7 - Flash point	-	-	-	-	-
8 -Trace metals mg/kg					
Iron	≤ 3.0	≤ 3.0	≤ 3.0	≤ 3.0	≤ 3.0
Copper	≤ 0.1	≤ 0.1	≤ 0.1	≤ 0.1	≤ 0.1
9 - Fatty acid ethyl esters (FAEEs) (mg/kg)	≤ 35				

This determination is solely for application by commercial partners on an optional basis.

** Commercial partners in the country of retail sale may require compliance with these limits when the oil is made available to the end consumer.

300

301 | 2.2.2. Chemical composition and bioactivity

302 Olive oil is basically composed of two fractions: the saponifiable and unsaponifiable
 303 fractions. The saponifiable fraction represents approximately 98% of the oil weight. It is
 304 mainly formed by fatty acids (esterified to glycerol) and other minor components, such
 305 as free fatty acids, phospholipids, waxes, and sterol esters. On the other hand, the
 306 unsaponifiable fraction, which represents approximately 2% of the total weight,

307 encompasses a complex set of minor compounds pertaining to chemical families such as
 308 aliphatic and triterpenic alcohols, sterols, hydrocarbons, phenols, tocopherols, esters, and
 309 pigments and volatile components such as aldehydes, ketones and alcohols (Dabbou et
 310 al., 2009; Guillén et al., 2009; Rjiba et al., 2011; Servili et al., 2013).

311 Because VOO is extracted only via physical methods without increasing its temperature
 312 or using chemical solvents, it especially preserves the concentration of minor compounds.

313 Table 2 lists the fatty acid compositional limits adopted by the International Olive Council
 314 (IOC, 2015a). MUFAs are the predominant fatty acids in olive oil, with oleic acid being
 315 the most abundant (55-83%) (Al-Bachir and Sahloul, 2016). As previously mentioned,
 316 the monounsaturated profile of fatty acids is one of the factors that contribute to explain
 317 the healthy benefits of olive oil in the Mediterranean Diet. Apart from oleic acid, it is
 318 worth mentioning another concentrated fatty acid, linoleic acid, which is an essential
 319 polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA) of nutritional interest (Piroddi et al., 2016;
 320 Schwingshackl and Hoffmann, 2014; Vannice and Rasmussen, 2014).

321 Table 2. Fatty acids composition limits adopted by the IOC ((International Olive Council, 2015).

Fatty Acid	Formula	Concentration (%)
Myristic acid	C14:0	< 0.03
Palmitic acid	C16:0	7.50 - 20.00
Palmitoleic acid	C16:1	0.30 - 3.50
Heptadecanoic acid	C17:0	< 0.30
Heptadecenoic acid	C17:1	< 0.30
Stearic acid	C18:0	0.50 - 5.00
Oleic acid	C18:1	55.00 - 83.00
Linoleic acid	C18:2	3.50 - 21.00
Linolenic acid	C18:3	< 1.00
Arachidic acid	C20:0	< 0.60
Gadoleic acid	C20:1	< 0.40
Behenic acid	C22:0	< 0.20
Lignoceric acid	C24:0	< 0.20

322

323 Phospholipids (PLs) are found in small quantities in olive oil (typically <150 mg/kg), but
 324 they play an important role in the syntheses of PUFAs, and they play a key role in
 325 membrane cell construction and the transmission of signals between cells (Alves et al.,
 326 2016; Boukhchina et al., 2004; Küllenberg de Gaudry et al., 2012). VOO and EVOO do

327 not contain waxes because they are not extracted via mechanical processing. Therefore,
328 the concentration of waxes and wax esters may be an indicator for detection of fraudulent
329 mixtures (Giuffrè, 2013; Mailer et al., 2010). One other chemical family used for fraud
330 detection is phytosterols, which are also nutritionally interesting since they contribute to
331 reducing total cholesterol and LDL-cholesterol in blood (Hassanein et al., 2016; St-Onge
332 et al., 2003; Vivancos and Moreno, 2008). Among olive oil phytosterols, it is worth
333 mentioning sitosterol, campesterol, stigmasterol, avenasterol and stigmastadienol.

334 Olive oil is also a reliable source of α -tocopherol, a molecule with vitamin E activity. The
335 concentrations of tocopherols found in olive oil range from 10 to approximately 350
336 mg/kg. α -Tocopherol is one of the most important lipophilic minor compounds found in
337 olive oil owing to its antioxidant activity contributing to health benefits and olive oil
338 shelf-stability. Nevertheless, the presence of this compound is not exclusive to olive oil.

339 Other refined oils, such as sunflower oil, are characterized by higher levels of tocopherols
340 (Ambra et al., 2016; Parveen et al., 2015; Psomiadou and Tsimidou, 1999).

341 The main triterpenes present in olive oil are oleanolic acid, ursolic acid, maslinic acid,
342 uvaol, and erythrodiol. Several authors have reported that the triterpenes concentration
343 can reach levels greater than 100 mg/kg (Allouche et al., 2009). As previously mentioned
344 for table olives, bioactive properties of triterpenes have been reported (Martín et al., 2009;
345 Sánchez-Quesada et al., 2015, 2013). Squalene is a natural polyunsaturated triterpene and
346 the major hydrocarbon found in olive oil, making up more than 90% of this fraction.

347 Squalene is essential for the biosynthesis of steroids and triterpenes and, at the same time,
348 constitutes an intermediate in the biosynthesis of phytosterols. Furthermore, several lines
349 of evidence highlight the numerous benefits of squalene to human health, such as
350 anticancer, antioxidant and cardioprotective activities (Cárdeno et al., 2015; Owen et al.,
351 2000; Popa et al., 2015; Salvo et al., 2017; Sánchez-Fidalgo et al., 2015). Some authors

352 also suggest that squalene plays an important role in the management of inflammatory
353 conditions (Cárdeno et al., 2015). On the other hand, squalene does directly influence
354 olive oil stability, but its chain-breaking ability contributes to regenerate α -tocopherol
355 (Psomiadou and Tsimidou, 1999; Velasco and Dobarganes, 2002).

356 The most important classes of pigments found in olive oil are carotenoids and chlorophyll
357 derivatives. Those compounds are responsible for the olive oil color, where chlorophylls
358 are associated with the green color and carotenoids with the yellow/orange color (Portilla
359 et al., 2014). Pigments, especially carotenoids, are associated with immune, endocrine
360 and metabolic benefits owing to their pro-vitamin A activity (Rao and Rao, 2007). The
361 concentration of pigments typically ranges from a few mg/kg to approximately 100
362 mg/kg, and they can be associated with the age and storage conditions, in addition to the
363 authenticity and quality of the olive oil (Ferruzzi and Blakeslee, 2007; Gandul-Rojas and
364 Minguéz-Mosquera, 1996; Lazzerini and Domenici, 2017).

365 Volatile compounds found in olive oil can be grouped into alcohols, aldehydes, esters,
366 ketones, sulfur compounds and terpenes (Procida et al., 2016). These compounds are
367 synthesized through different pathways, with some of them activated during the growing
368 of the fruit and others during and after the extraction of the olive oil by several enzymes
369 (such as lipoxygenase and alcohol dehydrogenase), and by oxidation reactions during
370 storage. Furthermore, the concentration of specific volatiles reveals the degradation or the
371 authenticity of olive oil (Guclu et al., 2016; Sghaier et al., 2016).

372 Finally, one of the most relevant chemical families of compounds found in olive oil is
373 that of phenolic compounds owing to the substantial number of research studies dedicated
374 to them. Several authors have reported the importance of phenolic compounds as
375 antioxidants and nutraceutical components (Bennett and Hayes, 2012; Britti et al., 2012;
376 Bulotta et al., 2014; Covas, 2008; Martínez-González et al., 2014). Additionally, they

377 play an important role in protection of olive oil from oxidation, making it more stable and
378 resulting in a longer shelf-life (Caponio et al., 2001; Farhoosh and Hoseini-Yazdi, 2013;
379 Silva et al., 2010). Most phenolic compounds identified and quantified in olive oil belong
380 to five different classes: phenolic acids (especially derivatives of benzoic and cinnamic
381 acids), flavonoids (luteolin and apigenin), lignans (pinoresinol and acetoxypinoresinol),
382 phenyl-ethyl alcohols (hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol) and secoiridoids (aglycon derivatives of
383 oleuropein and ligstroside). Within the great variability of phenolic groups, the role of
384 secoiridoids as conjugated forms of hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol is worth noting. This
385 group of compounds represents the most concentrated phenolic family in olive oil and is
386 being widely studied due to their promising healthy properties (Bendini et al., 2007; Del
387 Rio et al., 2016). This group of compounds, which are specific of the Oleacea family and
388 few others, includes oleuropein and ligstroside aglycon isomers and the
389 decarboxymethylated dialdehyde forms of oleuropein and ligstroside aglycones, which
390 are more frequently referred to as oleacein (3,4-DHPEA-EDA) and oleocanthal (p-
391 HPEA-EDA), respectively.

392 The most significant interest in phenolic compounds was spurred by the European Food
393 Safety Authority's (EFSA) scientific opinion that led to approving the health claim
394 included in the EU432/2012 Commission Regulation. The health claim is that "olive oil
395 phenols contribute to the protection of blood lipids from oxidative stress." This claim can
396 be included on the label only when the olive oil contains at least 5 mg of hydroxytyrosol
397 and its derivatives (e.g., oleuropein complex and tyrosol) per 20 g of olive oil (Casini et
398 al., 2014; EFSA, 2011; Martín-Peláez et al., 2013).

399 | 2.2.3. Organoleptic quality

400 The international method for the organoleptic assessment of VOO has been proposed by
401 the IOC (T.20/Doc. No 15/Rev. 8, November 2015). This method is only applicable to

402 VOOs and is based on the intensity of the defects and attributes perceived by a group of
403 tasters selected, trained and monitored as a panel. The main positive attributes are fruity,
404 bitter and pungent while defects include fusty, musty, winey, acid, rancid and wet wood,
405 among others (IOC, 2015b).

406 The sensory attributes of olive oil are ascribed to the strong stimulation of human sensory
407 receptors by both volatile and non-volatile compounds. Non-volatile components,
408 particularly phenols, stimulate the tasting receptors and the free endings of trigeminal
409 nerves, thereby eliciting the bitterness perception, pungency and astringency (Bendini et
410 al., 2007; Servili et al., 2004). These characteristics of olive oil are considered positive
411 attributes (Bendini et al., 2007; Ceci et al., 2017; Peyrot des Gachons et al., 2011).

412 On the other hand, volatile components stimulate the olfactive receptors and provide
413 positive or negative attributes to olive oil. Complete reviews regarding the volatile
414 composition of olive oil have been presented, and it is possible to find lists of detected
415 volatile compounds and, interestingly, their sensory attributes in the literature (Angerosa
416 et al., 2004; Kalua et al., 2005). The C6 and C5 compounds, with a special emphasis on
417 C6 linear unsaturated and saturated aldehydes (e.g., hexanal, cis/trans-hexenal, hexanol,
418 hexenol, acetate esters, pentenal, pentenol), represent the most important fraction of
419 volatile components, in quantitative terms, of virgin and extra virgin olive oils. The
420 “pungent-sweet-floral”, “floral”, “cooked-caramel”, “green-apple-cut”, “grass”, “citrus”,
421 “paperlike-fatty-sharp-cut” attributes are some of the principal positives attributes
422 associated with these compounds. However, some other pathways are responsible for the
423 negative attributes. These compounds are formed by sugar fermentation (winey), amino
424 acids (leucine, isoleucine and valine) conversion (fusty), enzymatic activities of molds
425 (musty), anaerobic microorganisms (muddy), and auto-oxidative processes (rancid)
426 (Procida et al., 2016).

427 The contribution of volatile compounds to the overall aroma of virgin olive oil depends
428 not only on their concentration but also on their sensory threshold values (Angerosa et
429 al., 2004; Kalua et al., 2005). In addition, antagonism and/or synergism among different
430 molecules can occur and affect the final flavor of olive oil. Chemical aspects of molecules
431 (volatility, hydrophobic character, size, shape, and conformational structure) and the type
432 and position of functional groups affect the sensory threshold value and, therefore, the
433 odor and taste intensity. These aspects all contribute to favor interaction with receptor
434 proteins and, for this reason, are more important than the concentration levels. Thus,
435 highly concentrated volatile compounds are not necessarily the major contributors of odor
436 (Angerosa et al., 2004; Essid et al., 2016).

437 |2.2.4. Storage process of olive fruits and olive oil

438 The quality of olive oil is related to not only the treatment and storage of the olive fruit
439 before processing (see section 5.8.) but also with the storage conditions of the olive oil
440 before consumption. Olive oil extracted from degraded fruits is usually characterized by
441 high acidity, low stability and undesirable sensorial attributes (Gutie et al. 1996;
442 Clodoveo et al. 2007).

443 The principal causes for the deterioration of olive oil during storage are oxidation and
444 hydrolysis reactions and the products of these reactions. Oxidation of lipids is promoted
445 by several factors, such as light, temperature, metals, concentration of pigments,
446 unsaturated fatty acid composition, levels and types of natural antioxidants and amount
447 of sterols. Lipid oxidation produces hydroperoxide molecules to form volatile compounds
448 that contribute to the typical undesirable oil defects “rancid”, “cucumber” and “muddy
449 sediment” (Angerosa et al., 2004; Méndez and Falqué, 2007). Additionally, the levels of
450 physiochemical quality parameters of olive oils, such as the ultra-violet light absorption
451 extinction coefficients (K_{232} and K_{270}), peroxide value (PV) and free acidity (FA), may

452 increase significantly during the storage of oil (Abbadı et al., 2014; Jabeur et al., 2015);
453 in contrast, the oxidative stability (OS) decreases (Stefanoudaki et al., 2010).
454 The changes that occur in the olive oil quality during the storage process also depend on
455 the chemical composition of the oil. First, non-filtered oil is more unstable than a filtered
456 oil, which is justified because non-filtered oils contain solids (fruit pulp particles) and
457 water in suspension, which promote the fermentation process and enzymatic reactions
458 and are responsible for unpleasant odors (Lozano-Sánchez et al., 2010). In contrast, the
459 main factors contributing to the oxidative stability of the olive oil are the ratio of MUFAs
460 to PUFAs (M/P ratio), tocopherol content and phenolic levels. The M/P ratio ranges from
461 4.0 to 9.2 and can be an appropriate measure of the tendency of olive oil to undergo
462 autoxidation. Higher ratios correspond to a higher oxidative stability of the olive oil.
463 Tocopherols and phenolics, with a synergic activity, are the most important antioxidant
464 compounds found in olive oils. During the storage time, a noticeable decrease in the levels
465 of secoiridoid derivatives, which are considered the most relevant antioxidant phenols in
466 olive oil (Hachicha Hbaieb et al., 2016, 2015), is observed.

467 **3. PHYSIOLOGICAL MECHANISMS AFFECTING YIELD AND QUALITY**

468 In this part, the changes during fruit growth and development affecting yield and quality
469 attributes are considered.

470 **3.1. Biennial bearing and the equilibrium between yield and quality**

471 Olive is a biennial bearing species in which developing fruits reduce shoot growth and
472 bloom return in nearby distal shoots. The sequence of high cropping (ON) and low
473 cropping (OFF) years is a well-known habit of olive (De Almeida, 1940; Lavee, 2007;
474 Rallo and Cuevas, 2017). From the horticultural point of view, several aspects of the
475 biennial bearing represent serious shortcomings for both the table olive and olive oil
476 sectors. ON cropping years are associated with small fruit size and late ripening. For table

477 olives, size is a major attribute for quality (e.g., considering ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’
478 olives, the main cultivar for Spanish-style green olives, those with weight < 2.5 g are
479 unmarketable for processing table olive, and these fruits are processed for oil).
480 Additionally, small-sized fruits in ON years impede the attainment of the maximum oil
481 content in any cultivar because the flesh-to-stone ratio and the percent of oil decrease
482 concomitantly at any time of harvest. However, the total amount of oil per tree and hectare
483 is always greater in ON than in OFF years. This biennial habit represents a logistic
484 constrain to fix the total storage capacity of the olive oil mills. Therefore, because the
485 olive oil yield represents a major concern in determining the harvest date, the biennial
486 bearing habit always represents a constrain for the farmer.

487 Some empirical and experimental approaches to partially modulate the imbalance
488 between cropping and quality, such as fruit thinning, have been developed for table olive
489 production. Additionally, pollination design and girdling have been used to increase
490 setting or flowering in OFF and ON years, respectively. Thus, modulating the imbalance
491 triggered by the difference in flowering between the ON and OFF years via different
492 practices may alleviate the inconveniences of biennial bearing. These practices include
493 fruit thinning at post bloom in table olives to reduce the fruit potential in ON years, and
494 prebloom girdling and pollination design to increase fruit set and development in OFF
495 years (Lavee et al., 1983; Rallo and Cuevas, 2017). However, some practices may modify
496 the oil composition. For instance, increasing irrigation leads to fruits with greater water
497 content (lower oil percentage), relative decreases in total polyphenol content and
498 increased free fatty acids in OFF years (Ben-Gal et al., 2011a).

499 Mechanisms related to inhibition of floral induction and with competition between fruits
500 and distal shoots are recognized as responsible for this biennial bearing. Recent results
501 indicate that the onset of dormancy in axillar buds is established soon after bud initiation

502 during the shoot-growing season; then, the leaves maintain bud dormancy until chilling
503 accumulation promotes the release of dormancy (Rallo and Cuevas, 2017). Whereas in
504 ON years, developing fruits inhibit floral induction, in OFF years, most axillary buds
505 develop into inflorescences the following year (Lavee et al., 1986; Rallo and Cuevas,
506 2017) once chilling accumulation overcomes bud dormancy and reproductive
507 development initiates. Recently, Haberman et al. (2017) found differences in the
508 quantitative expression of FT genes after winter rest between bud samples from previous
509 years OFF and ON trees, thus indicating some kind of “memory” expressed only once
510 buds develop reproductively at the end of dormancy.

511 3.2. Ripening physiology and quality

512 Ripening is defined as the final transformation of physiologically mature fruit. The
513 completion of fruit, seed and embryo growth is related to fruit maturation and precedes
514 ripening. Fruit ripening is associated with deep changes in color, firmness and
515 composition of the fruits and therefore affects quality. Ripening changes also trigger
516 natural fruit abscission. Maturity indices try to relate ripening stages to the time of harvest
517 maximizing oil yield and quality in the context of efficient orchard management.

518 |3.2.1. Determination of harvest maturity

519 From the horticultural point of view, the changes associated with ripening determine the
520 optimum time of harvesting, which depends on the final marketable products. In olive
521 growing, the time of harvest of table olives is related to the processing methods according
522 to the standards procedures established by the International Olive Council (IOC, 2004)
523 (see section 2.1.). For instance, for Spanish-style green olives, the time of harvesting is
524 determined by the change of external color from intense green to yellow green, which
525 usually occur at the time of maximum seed and embryo size (approximately 150 days
526 after full bloom (DAFB)) (Rapoport and Moreno-Alías, 2017). For oil-processed olives,

527 the time of harvest in traditional manually harvested orchards is the availability of
528 manpower, and harvesting olives starts after a purple external color is achieved and
529 extends for several months. Since the beginning of mechanical harvesting, the harvest
530 period has been drastically shortened, which allows advancing the time of harvest. The
531 following criteria determine the optimal harvest period: maximum oil accumulation; a
532 threshold for fruit retention force associated with the efficiency of the harvester; and a
533 maximum threshold for natural fruit abscission, all of which are related to the process of
534 ripening and the cultivar (Beltrán et al., 2017; Tombesi, 2003; Trapani et al., 2016).
535 Furthermore, the capacity to harvest olive mechanically in a short time has allowed
536 paying attention to the quality of the oil, which has become a new criterion for
537 determining the time of harvest. Figure 1 presents a calendar for the optimal harvest
538 period to maximize olive yield in a mechanically harvested orchard.

539

540 Figure 1. Relative size, relative oil and sugar content, and natural fruit abscission (%) related to the optimum
 541 harvest period (Bar). Elaborated from data from Beltrán et al., 2017; Humanes, 1975; Tombesi, 2003;
 542 Trapani et al., 2016.

543 DAFB – Days after Full Bloom, MI – Maturity Index (Uceda et al., 1980), FATH – Fruit Abscission Threshold: Maximum value 5-10%
 544 Bar – Harvest Period

545

546 3.2.2. Physicochemical - sensorial aspects during ripening

547 Within the period of harvesting, the physicochemical and sensorial attributes that enable
 548 specific organoleptic and nutraceutical profiles of virgin olive oils are analyzed to
 549 advance or delay the date of harvesting within the harvest period (Figure 1). As a rule,
 550 the farmer first guarantees the maximum olive oil yield and then specific virgin olive oil
 551 profiles. In this part, we summarize the main physico-chemical and sensorial changes
 552 (Table 3) and the changes in virgin olive oil compounds (Table 4) that occur during fruit
 553 ripening.

554

555 Table 3. Changes in physicochemical other traits and sensorial characteristics during fruit ripening.

Characteristics	Changes	References
Color	MI* from green (MI 0) to veraison (MI 2-3) to black (MI >4). Differences between cultivars and crop load.	Beltrán et al., 2017
Pigments	Chlorophyll and carotenoids disappear. Anthocyanins appear.	Beltrán et al., 2017; Tombesi, 2003
Firmness	Associated to pectic compounds. Anhydrous-galacturonic acid disappear with the advance of ripening. Changes associated with increase in softness starting at veraison (MI 2-3).	Tombesi, 2003
Respiration	Minimum value at veraison (MI 2-3).	Beltrán et al., 2017
Oil content	Sigmoid asymptotic accumulation from pit hardening (45 DAFB) to initial veraison (MI 2), i.e., 150 - 180 DAFB depending on cultivar and cropping. Then, oil content stabilizes.	Beltrán et al., 2017; Tombesi, 2003; Trapani et al., 2016
Time from Full Bloom to Veraison (MI 2-3)	Dependent from cultivar, temperature, water status and cropping. Thermal time may be a predictor between years.	Beltrán et al., 2017; Tombesi, 2003
Natural fruit abscission	Fruit retention force (FRF) avoids abscission before veraison (MI 2-3) then percentage of FRF decreases and fruit abscission progresses. Harvest should start before a threshold of fruit abscission (FATH) between 5-10%.	Beltrán et al., 2017; Humanes, 1975
Sensorial attributes	Bitter and pungency associated with oleuropein and total phenols. Peaks of volatiles appear at different times during ripening promoting different sensorial perceptions. For instance, trans-2-hexanal peak is associated to MI 1 early harvest.	Tombesi, 2003
Autoxidation and shelf life	See section 2.2.4.	

* Maturity Index (MI): 0. intense-green skin, 1. green-yellow skin, 2. skin with reddish-purple spots, 3. skin mostly purple, 4. skin black and flesh white, 5. skin black and flesh partially purple, 6. skin black and flesh mostly purple, 7. skin black and flesh fully purple (Uceda et al., 1980)

556

557

Compound group	Observations	References
Fatty acids	During fruit growth, the amount of all fatty acids increases. After veraison no significant changes in oil content and in fatty acids occur. Eventually small changes in oleic and linoleic are observed. Differences in oil content, fatty acid and triacylglycerol profiles are genotype dependent. Standardizing the time of maturity for sampling allows the selection of genotypes in breeding programs	Beltrán et al., 2017; De la Rosa et al., 2013; Famiani et al., 2002; Sánchez de Medina et al., 2015a; Vekiari et al., 2010; Yorulmaz et al., 2013
Tocopherols	α -Tocopherol is associated with antioxidant capacity and both variables decrease during FR. γ -Tocopherol increases during FR	Baccouri et al., 2008; Beltrán et al., 2010; Georgiadou et al., 2016
Phytosterols	β -Sitosterol decreases from September to November while δ -5-avenasterol increases with the maturation. The most important variables for differentiating fresh oils according to degree of ripening were δ -7-campesterol/ β -sitosterol, uvaol/stigmasterol, clerosterol/ δ -5-avenasterol and sitostanol/uvaol.	Fernandez-Cuesta et al., 2013; Gutiérrez et al., 2000; Lukić et al., 2013; Yorulmaz et al., 2013
Triterpenes	Triterpenoids represent the major triterpenic compounds of the fruit. Triterpenic diols are replaced by triterpenic acids during ripening. Maslinic acid is the main triterpenoid, only accompanied by oleanolic acid in the fruit and decreases during ripening. Squalene, a polyunsaturated triterpene, increases from fruit green to veraison and then stabilizes in correspondence to the maximum oil content	Fernandez-Cuesta et al., 2013; Guinda et al., 2010; Stiti et al., 2007
Volatiles	Volatile compounds appear during ripening and are associated with different fruit sensorial attributes. The volatile profile is cultivar dependent and has been used for cultivar discrimination. Hexanal and hexyl acetate-both produced from linoleic acid-are major contributors to the ripeness characterization. The most important contributors to olive oil aroma are C-6 aldehydes, alcohols, and esters. Specifically, the concentration of total esters, carbonyl, C6 and C5 increases or decreases with the ripening degree according to the cultivars, site and available water in the orchard.	Angerosa and Basti, 2001; Aparicio and Morales, 1998; Cevik et al., 2014; Dhifi et al., 2005; Gomez-Rico et al., 2006; Hbaieb et al., 2017; Kalua et al., 2005; Toker et al., 2016; Tombesi, 2003
Phenols	During ripening, the profile of phenolic compounds of different cultivars undergo wide modifications that strongly influence sensorial attributes, shelf life and nutritional value if olive and olive oil. Very large differences and peculiar trends between cultivars in the content of oleuropein, demethyloleuropein, ligstroside, tyrosol, hydroxytyrosol, verbascoside and lignans have been reported. Oleuropein is the major component of many cultivars and decline from green maturation to black ripen fruits. Degradation of oleuropein during ripening is concomitant with the accumulation of demethyloleuropein, oleuropein and total phenols.	Alagna et al., 2012; Amiot et al., 1989; El Riachy et al., 2011; Gomez-Rico et al., 2006; Servili, 2014; Servili et al., 2016; Tombesi, 2003; Tombesi et al., 2009
Pigments	Chlorophyll and carotenoids disappear. Anthocyanins appear at veraison and increases afterwards	Tombesi, 2003

559 | 3.2.3. Applicability of harvest maturity indices

560 Over the last 20 years, the olive oil sector has become increasingly concerned with
561 quality. Production systems such as integrated and organic production, Denomination of
562 Origin (DOP), and Geographic Indications (GI) are trying to find specific segments of
563 consumers to add value to their virgin olive oils. Despite the explicit differences in their
564 criteria for quality, these systems of production all agree regarding the quality attributes
565 reviewed in this work. In any case, there is a common target in all these systems, i.e.,
566 determining the optimal time of harvest

567 The Maturity Index (MI), which is usually referred as Ripening Index (RI), the days after
568 full bloom (DAFB) to reach any MI and the oil content expressed in dry and fresh weight
569 are the most widely used variables to determine the optimal time of harvest. Other
570 important trait is the natural fruit abscission threshold, which determines the final date for
571 harvest (Figure 1). For the production of high-quality virgin olive oils, other quality
572 attributes are also measured (see Tables 3 and 4).

573 Many experimental works have been done in different countries trying to determine the
574 optimal period for harvesting. The reported values in these works changed according to
575 cultivar, site, year and growing practices (Ben Youssef et al., 2010; Bodoira et al., 2015;
576 Dag et al., 2014, 2011; Jimenez et al., 2014; Lazzez et al., 2011; Romero et al., 2002;
577 Salvador et al., 2001; Trapani et al., 2016). For instance, the MI (RI) recommended ranges
578 for 'Picudo' and 'Hojiblanca' in Cordoba (Spain) are 2.8- 3.1 and 2.7-4.2, respectively
579 (Jimenez et al., 2014); for 'Arauco' in Rioja (Argentina), the range is 1-2 (Bodoira et al.,
580 2015); for 'Barnea', 'Coratina' and 'Picual' in the Jordan Valley (Israel), the ranges are
581 2.1-2.5, 2.3 and 3.2, respectively (Dag et al., 2011); for 'Chemlali' in Sfax (Tunisia), the
582 range is 2.5-3.5 (Lazzez et al., 2011); and for 'Cornicabra' in Toledo (Spain), the range
583 is 3.0-4.5 (Salvador et al., 2006).

584 During ripening, the oil content expressed on a dry weight basis is generally stable after
585 veraison (MI 2-3) changing the oil content expressed in fresh weight due to differences
586 in water content. Fatty acid composition profiles exhibit little changes, but minor
587 compounds may change within the cultivar in a different manner; i.e., there is an
588 interaction between the cultivar and MI for many minor compounds of the virgin olive
589 oil (see Tables 3 and 4). Therefore, the optimal MI score for harvest should be
590 complemented with analytical data of the compounds determining the farmer's target
591 quality for their virgin olive oil. In fact, all of the experiments described above represent
592 empirical approaches to establishing a safe farming strategy that balances the oil quantity
593 and desired quality.

594 3.3. **Secondary metabolic pathways associated with sensory or bioactive quality**

595 **attributes**

596 As previously explained, the detection of quality attributes in olive fruit and oil is directly
597 associated with molecules involved in secondary metabolic pathways. Therefore, it is key
598 to understand the biosynthetic pathways involved in the formation of phenols and volatile
599 compounds, in addition to the main factors contributing to regulate them. Two main
600 pathways have been proposed for the biosynthesis of secoiridoids in olive fruits, both
601 ending in the synthesis of oleuropein, even though this glycoside phenol is rarely detected
602 in olive oil. These two pathways are mechanistically diverse. The first pathway, proposed
603 in 1993 by Damtoft et al. (1993), is initiated by mevalonic acid for the formation of
604 iridoids and then to ligstroside, which is the precursor of oleuropein. An alternative
605 pathway was proposed in 2002 by Ryan et al. (2002), with tyrosol as a precursor produced
606 via phenylpropanoid biosynthesis. In this second mechanism, tyrosol is the substrate of
607 two synthetic schemes that led to a common final product, oleuropein. The first scheme
608 deals with ligstroside as intermediate, whereas the second one goes through oleacein and

609 oleuropein aglycon before its final conversion into oleuropein. Both synthetic pathways
610 would occur at the first ripening stages to accumulate oleuropein in the fruit.

611 At advanced maturation and especially during olive oil extraction, enzymatic and non-
612 enzymatic bio-transformations are produced to form the secoiridoid derivatives present
613 in olive oil. The most complete biotransformation pathway was proposed by Obied et al.
614 (2008), who explained the appearance of secoiridoid derivatives from oleuropein as a
615 precursor. In this pathway, oleuropein is converted into several derivatives according to
616 the involvement of two enzymes, esterases and β -glucosidases. Depending on the reaction
617 mechanism, oleuropein can be mainly converted to oleuropein aglycon isomers or to
618 oleacein via the following two main routes. The most important difference between the
619 routes is the typology of the enzymes involved. Thus, the formation of oleuropein aglycon
620 isomers is performed by β -glucosidase, which is activated during crushing and
621 malaxation. The second route is characterized by the involvement of methylesterases to
622 cleave the methyl group part of the elenolic acid. This second route would be responsible
623 for the formation of oleacein. The same conversions would occur for ligstroside to
624 preferentially produce ligstroside aglycon isomers and oleocanthal. The genotype and
625 agronomical and technical factors are critical to obtain a particular phenolic profile since
626 a variation in them could favor the kinetics of certain enzymatic processes.

627 Volatile compounds are rapidly formed during VOO extraction because of enzymatic
628 activities included in the lipoxygenase (LOX) pathway. The LOX pathway encompasses
629 a set of endogenous enzymes that use lipids as substrates to activate a series of events that
630 lead to volatile compounds responsible for the positive attributes detected in olive oil
631 (e.g., fruity, mature, apple, almond). As previously mentioned, the positive attributes are
632 strongly associated with the C6 and C5 compounds, especially with C6 linear unsaturated
633 and saturated aldehydes. In contrast, volatile components such as C7-C11

634 monounsaturated aldehydes, C6-C10 dienals, C5 branched aldehydes and alcohols or
635 some C8 ketones can reach relatively high concentrations in olive oils that are
636 characterized by organoleptic defects or off-flavors.

637 As Figure 2 shows, C6 and C5 volatiles are enzymatically produced from PUFAs through
638 the LOX pathway, in which the activity of the involved enzymes influences the
639 concentrations of compounds. The pathway consists of the formation of 9- and 13-
640 hydroperoxides from linoleic and linolenic acids with subsequent cleavage by specific
641 hydroperoxide lyases to produce C6 aldehydes, namely, hexanal, cis-hexenal and trans-
642 hexenal. Alcohols, primarily hexanol and hexenol isomers, are synthesized via the
643 reduction of C6 aldehydes by alcohol dehydrogenase enzyme. In the same manner,
644 alcohols can lead to acetate esters by alcohol acetyl transferases.

645 An additional pathway for linolenic acid as substrate is the formation of 1,3-pentene
646 radicals that can dimerize to C10 hydrocarbons or react with hydroxy radicals to form C5
647 alcohols, which can be oxidized enzymatically into C5 carbonyl compounds such as 2-
648 pentenal or 1-penten-3-one (Angerosa et al., 2004).

649 As an example, water stress conditions stimulate the synthesis of phenolic compounds in
650 olive fruits but exert a negative influence on volatile compounds related to the LOX
651 pathway (Servili et al., 2007).

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Figure 2. Pathway for the formation of major volatile compounds in virgin olive oil and enzymes involved in the production (adapted from Kalua et al., 2005, with permission of Elsevier).

657 4. BREEDING FOR OLIVE QUALITY: THE GENOTYPIC INFLUENCE

658 Cultivated olive still mostly consists of a broad diversity of traditional and clonally
659 propagated cultivars, which are presumably very old and of uncertain pedigree (Diez et
660 al., 2015; Trujillo et al., 2014). These traditional cultivars have been the foundation for
661 the solid and extensive rainfed olive growing system that has developed over centuries.

662 However, lately, olive cultivation has been changing radically. The yield has risen owing
663 to increasing irrigation and high-density planting. Accordingly, most new olive orchards
664 are designed for mechanical harvesting and early fruit-bearing. This new paradigm of
665 olive growing imposes significant changes that affect, among others, the characteristics
666 of successful cultivars. However, only a handful of traditional cultivars fit the
667 requirements needed for high-density systems. For instance, few alternatives to the use of
668 ‘Arbequina’, ‘Arbosana’ and ‘Koroneiki’ are found for the new narrow hedgerow (>1,500
669 olive/ha) plantation system (Diez et al., 2016; Rallo et al., 2013; Rosati et al., 2013). In
670 addition, irrigated high-density plantation systems have been related to a higher incidence
671 of certain diseases compared with standard rainfed orchards (Rallo et al., 2013). These
672 included airborne defoliating fungus diseases and Verticillium wilt caused by the fungus

673 *Verticillium dahliae* Kleb. Despite the recent outbreak of *Xylella fastidiosa* in the south
674 of Italy, *Verticillium* wilt is currently the most important diseases affecting this tree in the
675 majority of olive-growing countries (Jiménez-Díaz et al., 2012; López-Escudero and
676 Mercado-Blanco, 2011). Unfortunately, most of the olive cultivars evaluated to date are
677 susceptible or extremely susceptible to *V. dahliae* (Garcia-Ruiz et al., 2014; López-
678 Escudero et al., 2004; Trapero et al., 2015, 2013).

679 Thus, breeding of new cultivars that maintain the inherent genetic diversity of the
680 traditional cultivars but also address the requirements of intensive plantation systems and
681 resistance to airborne fungus diseases and *Verticillium* wilt is required. In addition, given
682 the forecast for climate change in the Mediterranean Basin and its possible effects on
683 olive growth (Ponti et al., 2014), breeding olive cultivars with different chilling
684 requirements might also be crucial for the sustainability of olive growing in the future.

685 Olive breeding programs are relatively new compared with other fruit species. The first
686 olive breeding programs using cross-breeding were initiated between 1960 and 1971 in
687 Israel (Lavee, 1990) and Italy (Bellini et al., 2002), respectively. Since the mid-1980s,
688 new breeding programs, mostly focused on obtaining cultivars for olive oil production,
689 have been developed in France (1986), Spain (1991), Morocco (1994), Tunisia (1994),
690 Turkey (1994), Greece (1996), Australia (1997), Iran (1999), and Portugal (2002) (de la
691 Rosa and León., 2009). Most of these programs have been focused on obtaining cultivars
692 for olive oil, and only a few have focused on table olive or both (Rallo et al., 2011). To
693 date, only the programs from Israel, Italy, and Spain have released new cultivars,
694 producing a total of 14 new cultivars (De la Rosa and León., 2009).

695 A procedure consisting of three basic steps is generally performed to select outstanding
696 individuals. This procedure starts with directed crosses between cultivars, followed by
697 selection within the progenies and finally the cloning of outstanding individuals

698 (advanced selections) exhibiting high oil production and eventually early bearing, in
699 addition to adaptation to mechanical harvesting and high-density plantations (Rallo,
700 2014). To date, in most olive oil breeding programs, the total oil content is still the main
701 trait that is selected for. Normally, only advanced selections are further characterized in
702 terms of their oil fatty acid profiles and minor compounds content due to the high labor
703 cost of these processes (Leon et al., 2008; León et al., 2011). Similarly, in the case of
704 table olives, the size of the fruit, shape and flesh-to-stone ratio are the main selection
705 criteria in the first stages of large progenies evaluation, whereas the analysis of table olive
706 compounds, such as sugars, phenolics and triterpenic acids, has been limited to a few
707 selected genotypes (Rallo et al., 2012; Medina et al., 2012). However, health concerns are
708 becoming one of the major driving forces of the world food market (Byrne, 2012);
709 therefore, obtaining new cultivars with health-enhancing properties is progressively
710 becoming the focus of olive breeding programs (De la Rosa et al., 2016)

711 As has been described in previous sections, both virgin olive oil and table olives are staple
712 products that contribute to the health benefits of the Mediterranean Diet. This is mainly
713 due to their unsaturated fatty acid profile and the presence of other compounds with
714 proven bioactive properties, such as tocopherols, squalene, pigments, triterpenic acids and
715 phenolic compounds. The increasing awareness of the health benefits of food and the
716 willingness of consumers to pay a premium for them is creating a new market for fruit
717 crops cultivars with health-enhanced properties (see Byrne, 2012 and Wargovich et al.,
718 2012 for a complete review). Thus, products from olives (virgin olive oil and table olives)
719 are perfect candidates to be considered “superfoods”, a marketing term that can boost the
720 consumption of the target product, which is touted to have exceptional health benefits.
721 For instance, blueberries and pomegranate have enjoyed significantly increased

722 consumption in only a few years as a result of their high anthocyanin content and
723 consideration as “superfruits”.

724 The central requirement to start a breeding program with the goal of increasing the content
725 of certain compounds is the availability of genotypic variation for these compounds
726 among the cultivars to be used as genitors. Several studies have noted the remarkable
727 genetic diversity and heterozygosity of traditional olive cultivars (Diez et al., 2015;
728 Trujillo et al., 2014), and others have already proven how this variability translates in
729 terms of oil fatty acid composition (Aguilera et al., 2017) and content of some bioactive
730 compounds (Beltrán et al., 2016, 2010; Kyçyk et al., 2016; Sánchez de Medina et al.,
731 2015a, 2015b). Most of these studies have also shown that the effect of the genotype is
732 the main factor responsible of this variation, although it is modulated by yearly variation
733 and edaphoclimatic differences between orchard locations. Nevertheless, the influence of
734 the cultivars in many of the quality traits mentioned in sections 2.1. and 2.2. is still
735 unexplored (Rallo et al., 2011).

736 On the other hand, this high variability and heterozygosity make necessary the evaluation
737 of a vast number of individuals within progenies. The influences of genitors and crosses
738 on olive oil composition (De la Rosa et al., 2016, 2008; El Riachy et al., 2012; Leon et
739 al., 2008, 2004b) and on other characteristics, such as the time to reach flowering (Moral
740 et al., 2013), the tree vigor (Santos-Antunes et al., 2005), and the resistance to *Verticillium*
741 wilt (Trapero et al., 2015), have been demonstrated. However, the variability observed
742 within olive progenies has always been greater than that between progenies and genitors,
743 with individuals frequently exhibiting transgressive segregation (De la Rosa et al., 2016;
744 Leon et al., 2004a; Trapero et al., 2015).

745 The need to evaluate large progenies requires the application of clear selection criteria
746 based on easily measurable traits in addition to the optimization of tools to simplify and

747 automatize the selection process. For instance, the application of near infrared reflectance
748 spectroscopy (NIRS) to evaluate characters such as the oil content, moisture, and fatty
749 acid composition in intact olive fruits has provided reliable, fast and accurate
750 determination of these characteristics (León et al., 2003; 2004c; Morales-Sillero et al.,
751 2011). Additionally, optimized protocols, based on the application of chromatography
752 techniques, have revealed a high correlation between the compositions of olive fruit and
753 olive oil in terms of fatty acids (Garces and Mancha, 1993), tocopherol, sterol and
754 squalene (Velasco et al., 2014), allowing the evaluation of olive progenies at the initial
755 steps of selection (De la Rosa et al., 2016).

756 Indirect selection, based on the linkage between different traits, has also simplified and
757 accelerated the screening process. This has been the case for the relationship between the
758 high seedling vigor (height and trunk diameter) and its early flowering in olive (De la
759 Rosa et al., 2006; Moreno-Alfías et al., 2010). This relationship has allowed more than
760 40% of olive seedlings with long juvenile phases to be discarded just a few months after
761 their germination (Rallo et al., 2008).

762 The recent publication of the olive reference genome (Cruz et al., 2016) and the expected
763 development of early markers for selection will accelerate the long breeding cycles of this
764 crop. The primary use of genomics in breeding is marker-assisted selection (MAS) for
765 traits controlled by major genes or quantitative trait loci (QTLs). Via MAS, genetic
766 markers that are either known to cause a phenotype or are strongly linked to the causal
767 genetic variant can be genotyped at the seedling stage, thus enabling prediction of the
768 phenotype of the adult plant (Rallo et al., 2016). Since the cost of phenotyping is likely
769 to increase in the future, whereas the cost of genotyping has decreased considerably over
770 time, and this trend is expected to continue (McClure et al., 2014), generalization of
771 genomic tools for the characterization of genetic resources and the selection of candidate

772 genotypes is expected to become a general trend in plant breeding. These new
773 technologies will also increase our knowledge about the genetic control and expression
774 of bioactive compounds in fruit crops and specifically in olive, thereby opening new
775 possibilities for breeding olive cultivars with specific bioactive profiles.

776 **5. ENVIRONMENTAL AND AGRONOMIC FACTORS AFFECTING OLIVE**

777 **QUALITY**

778 **5.1. Soil**

779 Olive trees may be cultivated in a great diversity of soils, but some of them limit tree
780 development and fruit and oil quality. Soil properties affect water availability, and this,
781 in turn, may affect fruit ripeness and weight and oil quality. Bucelli et al. (2011) found
782 that the quality of the fruits and oils from ‘Frantoio’ and ‘Moraiolo’ cultivars, both
783 growing under rainfall conditions, differed depending on the soil properties, in particular,
784 the soil water availability. In soils with low clay content or low moisture content,
785 potassium deficiency symptoms are often found, and fruit may exhibit smaller sizes and
786 even wrinkling. In contrast, high pH and calcareous soils favor iron chlorosis, which
787 decreases the value of table olives with a smaller size and chlorotic color of the skin. In
788 these soils, boron deficiencies are also frequent and may induce fruit malformations. In
789 contrast, in low-pH and thus acidic soils, the lack of calcium may affect table olive quality
790 by the decrease of pulp firmness (Fernandez-Escobar, 2017) and favor the higher
791 incidence of Anthracnose disease, which decreases the quality of both fruits and oil
792 (Moral et al., 2014). Magnesium deficiencies can also be found in acids in addition to
793 sandy soils, in which fruits also acquire chlorotic appearance.

794 **5.2. Climate**

795 Olive is usually grown in warm areas characterized by cool-to-mild winters and warm-
796 to-hot summers, with most rainfall events occurring from autumn to spring. Frost damage

797 occurs when the temperature decreases below 0 °C. Fruits at -1.7 °C may exhibit surface
798 blisters and spots, and they may have aqueous consistency and drop or remain wrinkled
799 until harvest. At -3 °C or lower temperature, fruit freezing occurs, negatively affecting
800 table olive quality as a consequence of cell dehydration and the destruction of the cells
801 by ice crystals provoking oxidative processes (Sanzani et al., 2012). The oil quality also
802 decreases by losses in the stability to oxidation, which are related to the decreases in the
803 concentration of the most phenolic compounds, particularly secoiridoid derivatives.
804 Sensorial analysis of these oils reveals less pungent taste and absence of bitter taste
805 (Morelló et al., 2003). In contrast, high summer temperatures may induce the presence of
806 redness or dried spots on the surface of olives and over-maturation of the olive fruit,
807 whereas in the oil, increases in free acidity and the content of palmitoleic and linoleic
808 fatty acids and a decrease in oleic acid content have been reported (Orlandi et al., 2012).
809 Moreover, a high temperature during the ripening period negatively affects fruit weight,
810 oil content and even fatty acid composition since oleic acid decreases, a common fact in
811 EVOO from new warm cultivation areas (García-Inza et al., 2014; Inglese et al., 2011;
812 Rondanini et al., 2014). For phenols, the effect of high temperature is not yet clear.
813 Whereas Ripa et al. (2008) found that total phenol content decreases when high
814 temperatures accumulate from fruit set to harvesting, Tura et al. (2008) found that in cool
815 areas, the phenol content increases with degree-days accumulation in the same period.
816 Moreover, a warmer spring with sufficient rain in spring and autumn has a positive effect
817 on the oil's volatile composition (Tura et al, 2009).

818 Other abiotic factors may reduce both olive and oil quality, particularly wind and hail.
819 Winds may contribute, in combination with drought/high temperature conditions, to the
820 shriveling of the olives and favor bruising damage due to the beating of the fruits. In
821 addition, injuries caused by winds can induce entry points for pathogens. Blemishes and

822 malformations caused by hailstorms may also reduce table olive quality. They can also
823 induce injuries that favor internal tissue oxidation and consequently increase the free
824 acidity in the oil (Sanzani et al., 2012).

825 **5.3. Cultivation system**

826 For agronomic practices, the available literature demonstrates the importance of all of
827 them in terms of the production of quality. In the design of a new olive orchard, the choice
828 of tree density and the row orientation must be performed while considering the soil and
829 climate conditions and the water availability and quality. An excessive tree density and/or
830 vigor may imply competition for light among trees reducing fruit size, oil quantity and
831 quality. Particular attention should be given to olive hedgerow orchards, which have been
832 developed since the 1990s, because the choices of row spacing and row orientation
833 determine the illumination of the walls, which can affect the mesocarp size and
834 composition (water and oil) (Trentacoste et al., 2016). Furthermore, high-density
835 conditions may create ventilation problems that favor diseases development (Moral et al.,
836 2014).

837 **5.4. Canopy management**

838 Canopy management (pruning, fertilization and water in the case of irrigated orchards),
839 is key for the control of vigor, interception of solar radiation and fruit load regulation. An
840 appropriate canopy management strategy, adapted to the cultivation system, is necessary
841 to favor solar radiation interception and porosity to maximize olive yield and the
842 efficiency of mechanical harvesting. The light environment around the canopy of tree is
843 not uniform. Olive fruits located in zones of the canopy that are significantly exposed to
844 solar radiation, such as the top, are larger and tend to have oblong shapes; they ripen faster
845 and produce more oil than fruits located in shadow zones, such as the lower parts and
846 inner zones of the trees (Bartolini et al., 2014; Benelli et al., 2014; Connor et al., 2014).

847 Furthermore, the oil quality varies according to the fruit position in the canopy, and the
848 oils from fruits that are highly exposed to light, usually from the middle-outer and upper
849 canopy, exhibit higher phenol content (Castillo-Ruiz et al., 2015), greater stability to
850 oxidation, high palmitic and linoleic acid contents and lower oleic acid content compared
851 with oils from lower-canopy fruit (Gómez del Campo and García, 2012). The influence
852 of crop load should also be considered because fruit size and the flesh-to-stone ratio
853 usually increase with low fruit load (Gucci et al., 2007; Trentacoste et al., 2010).
854 Therefore, for highly bearing cultivars, adequate pruning should trend to equilibrate the
855 fruit load. Furthermore, mechanical pruning has been recently developed for intensive
856 and super-high-density orchards as a way to decrease the production costs. Appropriate
857 management is needed to avoid the excessive development of new branches after cutting
858 of young branches, which may decrease solar radiation interception in the canopy (Gucci
859 and Cantini, 2000).

860 **5.5. Irrigation**

861 Olive tree responds positively to irrigation, a common practice in intensive and super-
862 high-density orchards. Strong drought in summer can lead to fruit ripening and negatively
863 influence the fruit size and flesh-to-stone ratio, even causing shriveling of the fruit,
864 although it does not affect the accumulation of oil (Bartolini et al., 2014). Irrigation
865 therefore increases the water content, fruit size and flesh-to-stone ratio. Nevertheless,
866 firmness, total phenols and sugar content can decrease with increased irrigation, although
867 no differences are observed in sensory characteristics after preservation in brine (Gucci
868 et al., 2007; Patumi et al., 2002; Proietti and Antognozzi, 1996).

869 Concerning oil quality, water stress conditions stimulate the synthesis of phenolic
870 compounds in olive fruits but exert a negative influence on volatile compounds related to
871 the LOX pathway (Servili et al. 2007, Bucelli et al., 2011). However, oils are occasionally

872 characterized as excessively bitter (Servilli et al., 2007). An increased water content in
873 the fruit can make it difficult to extract the oil (Grattan et al., 2006). In addition, although
874 the criteria for classifying in commercial categories have not been modified, oil quality
875 usually decreases with the loss of minor compounds, mainly phenols, and with changes
876 in their profiles (Patumi et al., 2002; Tovar et al., 2002). This may be particularly negative
877 for cultivars as ‘Arbequina’, whose oils are characterized by low stability to oxidation
878 (Romero et al., 2012). In contrast, irrigation offers an opportunity to modulate the
879 excessive bitterness of the oils of other cultivars, as ‘Cornicabra’ (Gómez-Rico et al.,
880 2007) and ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’ (Garcia et al., 1996). However, abundant precipitation
881 events can override the effects of irrigation on phenols (Garcia et al., 2017; Stefanoudaki
882 et al., 2009a).

883 Not only phenols but also volatile content and composition change with irrigation. Thus,
884 irrigation may favor the concentration of compounds responsible for green-fruity sensory
885 perceptions, such as (E)-hex-2-enal and (Z)-hex-2-enal, hexanal and hexan-1-ol (Gómez-
886 Rico et al., 2006; Servilli et al., 2009), but panels do not always identify differences in
887 flavor description of the VOOs (Morales-Sillero et al., 2013).

888 Recent studies regarding regulated deficit irrigation (RDI) have shown that an appropriate
889 strategy for controlling the moment and intensity of water restriction may result in
890 increased fruit weight, size, skin hardness and linoleic acid content (D’Andria et al., 2004;
891 Cano-Lamadrid et al., 2015; Grattan et al., 2006). It also favors saltiness, bitterness, green
892 olive note, aftertaste and hardness, after green processing of ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’
893 olives, thereby increasing consumer global acceptance compared with other irrigation
894 strategies (Cano-Lamadrid et al., 2015). An appropriate RDI strategy can also decrease
895 bruising damage (Casanova et al., 2017) and may increase the content of phytoprostane
896 (Collado-González et al., 2015). Regarding the oil quality, different studies are also now

897 showing that the application of deficit irrigation in summer is not only an imperative
898 option in many orchards but also the best for EVOO quality production, in particular, by
899 increasing the content of total phenols and sensory quality (García et al., 2017; Gómez-
900 Rico et al., 2007; Gómez del Campo and García, 2013). However, increases in the phenol
901 content with irrigation dose or no effect of this practice on oil quality have also been
902 reported (Dabbou et al., 2011; Tognetti et al., 2007), which means that VOO quality
903 depends on the cultivar and on the environment and management of the orchard.
904 Controversial or inconsistent results regarding oil content, fatty acid composition and
905 other traits, such as tocopherols, acidity, peroxide index or extinction coefficients, can
906 also be found (Gómez-Rico et al., 2007; Tovar et al., 2002; Stefanoudaki et al., 2009a).
907 An appropriate RDI strategy should be chosen considering the stress level and fruit load
908 (Ben-Gal et al., 2011b; Martín-Vertedor, et al., 2011). The quality of the water should
909 also be considered. Irrigation with saline water decreases fruit weight and oil content and
910 modifies the fatty acid composition, although it can also increase the contents of total
911 phenols and major phenols (Ben Ahmed et al., 2009; Stefanoudaki et al., 2009b).

912 **5.6. Fertilization**

913 Fertilization is especially necessary when trees are subject to deficiency conditions.
914 However, the influence of this practice on olives and oil quality has not been sufficiently
915 studied. Nitrogen is commonly employed in many orchards owing to its importance on
916 olive nutrition. Foliar applications of different fertilizers with or without N produce
917 decreased total phenol and tocopherol contents in addition to changes in the profiles of
918 minerals, sugars, phenols and tocopherols (Tekaya et al., 2014). High doses of nitrogen
919 applied by fertigation in combination with phosphorus and potassium increase the fruit
920 weight, flesh-to-stone ratio, potassium and water contents but also degrade the pulp
921 texture and decrease the total sugar content (Morales-Sillero et al., 2008). However, the

922 extent to which all of these changes observed in table olives influence sensory properties
923 or antioxidant activity is unknown. Regarding oil, there is a negative effect of an excess
924 of N fertilization on oil quality because the phenol content and, thus, the stability to
925 oxidation and bitterness decrease with an increased concentration of this element in the
926 fruit (Fernandez-Escobar et al., 2006). High N levels in the fruit also decrease the oleic
927 acid content. The effects of P and K fertilization on oil quality are minor and negligible,
928 respectively (Erel et al., 2013).

929 **5.7. Phytosanitary control**

930 Climate and agronomic practices as canopy management determine the sanitary status of
931 olive orchards. Phytosanitary control should prevent those plagues and diseases, such as
932 olive fly and Anthracnose, respectively, which have clear influences on the quality of
933 olives and the extracted oils. The olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*) is the most important
934 plague, and its abundance and distribution is favored by arid locations with hot summer
935 temperature. Larvae consume the pulp of fruits, thereby destroying tissues, which leads
936 to a severe fruit drop. Moreover, fruits are prone to fruit contamination. Large-size and
937 green fruits attract adult flies more than smaller and ripened fruits. Moreover, the wax
938 composition of the epicarp and volatile compounds emitted by fruits and leaves are
939 relevant for oviposition. Infested table olives exhibit browning spots, deformities or
940 mutilations, and a negative attribute, mustiness, is perceived in sensorial analyses.
941 Kinesthetic sensations are also drastically affected as a consequence of pulp consumption
942 and larvae development. Thus, fruits infested by *B. oleae* are not processed for table olive.
943 Concerning oil production, infested fruits are destined to industry extraction, but the oils
944 exhibit considerable increases in free acidity and extinction coefficients (K_{232} and K_{270})
945 that often prevent them from being classified as EVOO. Furthermore, stability to
946 oxidation and antioxidant capacity decrease due to reductions in phenol compounds (even

947 up to 80%) and in chlorophylls and carotenoids pigments, with the oil becoming lighter
948 in color and more golden-yellow than green. Sensory attributes, such as green, fruity and
949 cut grass, decrease with the loss of volatiles compounds, such as (*E*)-2-hexenal (Malherio
950 et al., 2015). Integrated pest management, including culture practices, such as the removal
951 of the fruits that remain in trees after harvest, are recommended to eradicate or reduce
952 infestations (Yokoyama, 2015).

953 Anthracnose, which it is caused by two species of *Colletotrichum*, is the most important
954 disease form the point of view of oil quality deterioration. The infection of the olives
955 increases after the first autumn rains and when the temperature is in the range of 17-20
956 °C. Mature fruits of highly susceptible cultivars are usually the most affected, showing
957 typical depressed spots of ocher or brown color and developing rot. The extracted oils
958 show a characteristic reddish color and increases in the free acidity, peroxide index,
959 extinction coefficients (K_{232} and K_{270}), phenol compounds and alkyl esters. The literature
960 regarding the effects on oil quality, however, is scarce (Moral et al., 2014).

961 5.8. **Harvesting**

962 Harvesting olives as intact and healthy as possible at the right time and proper subsequent
963 transport to the industry should guarantee production of table olives and oil of superior
964 quality. Table olives for Spanish-style green processing must be harvested at MI 1, i.e.,
965 when the epidermis color is green-yellowish, the fruits reach maximum size, and the pulp
966 is separated easily from the stone, which avoid excessive bruising damage. Harvesting of
967 black ripe or Californian-style can be delayed until the change of color in the skin, but the
968 proportion of fruits in this state should not exceed 20%. Naturally black or Greek-style
969 olives can be harvested later, although it is recommended not to delay harvesting too
970 much to avoid the degradation of texture (Sánchez and García, 2017).

971 The harvest timing is also a key for the production of EVOO. Determining the optimum
972 moment is, however, difficult because of the variability in the cultivar response between
973 growing seasons and the effect of fruit load on the maturity stage, because a high fruit
974 load delays fruit ripening (Dag et al., 2011). Harvesting at MI 3, which usually coincides
975 with maximum oil accumulation and good quality, is often recommended. Late harvesting
976 may lead to an excessive fruit drop and often results in oils with the lowest hydrophilic
977 phenol concentration and aromatic profile due to the minor LOX activity produced from
978 over-ripened olives (Servili et al., 2015). Increases in the free acidity and decreases in the
979 chlorophyll content, the M/P and saturated/unsaturated fatty acid ratios, and the fruitiness
980 perception in sensorial analyses have also been reported (Dag et al. 2011; Salvador et al.,
981 2001). In contrast, early harvesting, when the oil content is still increasing, usually results
982 in oils with higher phenol content, which contributes to the stability to oxidation and the
983 level of bitterness and pungency, although the latter positive attributes may be in some
984 cases excessive and unacceptable to consumers (Dag et al., 2011). Early harvesting can
985 also reduce the negative effects of irrigation on oil quality and prevent damages from frost
986 (Gracia et al., 2012), olive fly adult activity (Rojnic´et al., 2015) and Anthracnose (Moral
987 et al., 2014) and may contribute to preventing negative global warming because
988 cultivation under extreme climatic conditions (i.e., higher temperature and lower rainfall)
989 causes fruits to ripen faster (Dag et al., 2014). Moreover, harvesting at night to avoid the
990 effects of high temperature at harvest seems to improve the oil's sensory qualities (Di
991 Serio et al., 2014).

992 Manual harvesting is the best option to maximize the quality of table olive and oil.
993 However, mechanical harvesting is a necessary method to decrease cost in many orchards.
994 Trunk shakers are frequently used in olive orchards for oil production, but in the case of
995 table olive, they are mainly used for cultivars characterized by low susceptibility to fruit

996 damage, such as ‘Hojiblanca’. Other cultivars, such as ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’, exhibit
997 significant damage, such as bruising and cutting of the fruit, after trunk shaker harvesting.
998 The level of bruising is 12 times higher than when olives are hand-picked, and most
999 bruising occurs in the first hour after harvesting and exhibits an exponential increase after
1000 it (Jiménez-Jiménez et al.,2013). Post-harvest field immersion in a dilute solution of
1001 NaOH and transportation in liquid to industry have been proposed to reduce bruising
1002 (Rejano et al., 2008; Zipori et al., 2014). Strategies such as adaptation of tree pruning to
1003 reduce the canopy volume and to facilitate the transmission of the vibration, the
1004 adjustment of the vibration parameters of the trunk shakers, and post-harvest treatments
1005 have also been proposed to facilitate table olive harvesting using trunk shakers, in
1006 particular when the fruit is intended for green-style processing (Ferguson et al., 2010;
1007 Castro-Garcia et al., 2015). Recent studies about table olives have opened new interesting
1008 alternatives for mechanical harvesting via the use canopy contact harvesters (Ferguson et
1009 al., 2010), including those adapted from the grape straddle machines used in super-high-
1010 density hedgerows (Morales-Sillero et al., 2014).

1011 Despite the fact that mechanical harvesting of the olives for oil mill extraction is now a
1012 reality in many countries, studies of the effect of this method on oil quality are very scarce,
1013 probably because the production of EVOO is usually feasible in these conditions.
1014 However, losses of natural antioxidants and flavor components, and in some cases,
1015 increased free acidity, have been observed with different types of harvesters, either hand-
1016 vibrating combs (Dag et al., 2008) or grape straddle harvesters (Yousfi et al., 2013). This
1017 is probably a response to fruit internal damage caused by harvesters (Jiménez et al., 2017)
1018 and to physiological alterations to the fruit, such as increases in respiration rate and,
1019 mainly, ethylene production (Morales-Sillero and Garcia, 2015; Yousfi et al., 2013).
1020 Therefore, to minimize fruit and oil quality losses, it is important to search for a

1021 compromise between harvesting efficiency and fruit damage (Connor et al., 2014).
1022 Furthermore, to maintain the olives' quality, harvested fruits should not be mixed with
1023 fruits picked from the soil and the transport of the fruit must be performed as quickly as
1024 possible to minimize the time elapsed between harvesting and processing. Production of
1025 high-quality table olives and EVOO will be facilitated if fruits are transported separated
1026 by quality and in trailers or containers with limited cargo to avoid cramping and anaerobic
1027 conditions. Storage of olive fruits in adverse conditions, such as sacks or piles, negatively
1028 affects the sensorial quality of the oil. Under such conditions, diverse types of
1029 microorganisms proliferate, producing different undesired metabolites, such as branched
1030 aldehydes, alcohols and the corresponding carboxylic acids that contribute to negative
1031 attributes (typically the "fusty" defect). When the temperature is increased due to storage
1032 of fruits, yeasts produce ethanol and ethyl acetate, which are detected as the "winey"
1033 defect. In contrast, under low-temperature conditions, proliferation of fungi and yeast
1034 leads to the appearance of the "musty-humid" defect. To avoid these defects, it is
1035 recommended to process the fruits as soon as possible after harvest (Angerosa et al., 2004;
1036 Kalua et al., 2007).

1037

1038 6. CONCLUSIONS

1039 Quality itself is becoming a fundamental goal for most horticultural products, including
1040 table olives and olive oil, the two main products obtained from olive fruits. The concept
1041 of quality in olives is complex, and a large number of traits might be considered. Different
1042 definitions may apply according to the point of view and final goal of producers, traders,
1043 consumers and/or nutritionists. For example, legal quality refers to the standards to which
1044 both products must conform for trading purposes but is usually insufficient to define the
1045 holistic quality of table olives and olive oil. For table olives, traits related to fruit

1046 appearance, such as the size, shape, color or absence of damage in the surface are, among
1047 others, the most common quality criteria, whereas for olive oil, the quality is largely
1048 determined by its physico-chemical properties (e.g., free acidity, peroxide value, UV
1049 absorbency) and its composition.

1050 Consumers are becoming especially aware of the influence of food on human health, and,
1051 in this sense, a market niche for food products with preventive and therapeutic properties
1052 is rapidly emerging. Table olives and virgin olive oil may be considered as nutraceutical
1053 products since they are rich in many compounds with beneficial health effects. A
1054 significant body of literature about this matter has been published in medical and chemical
1055 journals, especially for olive oil, but table olives are also being studied from this point of
1056 view. In addition to the well-known benefits of the consumption of olive products derived
1057 from their fatty acid profile, which is rich in MUFAs and linoleic acid (PUFA), and from
1058 the high content of α -tocopherol (vitamin E), the roles of other compounds with bioactive
1059 activity are also being highlighted. Among them, triterpenic acids (maslinic and
1060 oleanolic), squalene and phenolic compounds (oleuropein complex, tyrosol and
1061 hydroxytyrosol) have been reported to exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer
1062 and cardioprotective activities, among others. The fact that olive products are among the
1063 top food sources containing these compounds enhances the nutritional interest in olive oil
1064 and table olives. In fact, the EFSA has approved a health claim label for olive oil
1065 exhibiting high contents of phenolic compounds.

1066 The particular sensorial attributes of olive oil and table olives are also gaining much
1067 interest among consumers. Non-volatile components, particularly phenols, and volatile
1068 compounds (especially the C6 and C5 compounds) determine the gustatory and olfactory
1069 perceptions of olive oil, respectively. For both products, standardized methods for sensory
1070 analysis are available.

1071 Although processing has very important effects on the quality of both products, and these
1072 effects have been studied extensively, the determination of olive quality begins in the
1073 field with decisions such as what cultivars should be used, where to plant, how to design
1074 and manage the orchard, and when and how to harvest the fruits to achieve the best
1075 possible quality. Unfortunately, less work has focused on these issues.

1076 Regarding plant material, olive cultivar diversity is extremely rich, and many of these
1077 traditional cultivars may produce table olives and EVOOs with high and distinct quality
1078 attributes. Nevertheless, most of these varieties remain unexplored in terms of some of
1079 the aforementioned quality traits, and further efforts should be made to evaluate them.

1080 Similarly, olive breeding programs are still few and relatively recent, but the focus on
1081 specific quality attributes in some of these programs, along with the development of
1082 genomic tools to accelerate the selection of interesting genotypes, will probably help to
1083 yield, in the midterm, new olive cultivars with enhanced quality.

1084 Regarding the influence of environmental conditions, soil properties (particularly the pH,
1085 the limestone content and deficiencies in certain elements) and climatic factors (low
1086 temperatures that may cause frost damage or high temperatures in summer) have been
1087 reported to affect the quality of olive fruits and, hence, the quality of their products.

1088 Among agronomical factors, particularly interesting is the choice of tree density and row
1089 orientation when establishing an orchard because these choices affect the interception of
1090 solar radiation by the fruits, which ultimately influences traits such as the fruit size, shape
1091 and oil content. Furthermore, increases in phenols, palmitic and linoleic content have been
1092 reported in fruits with greater exposure to light. In this sense, pruning is essential to
1093 manage the light environment in the canopy and to regulate the fruit load. Irrigation and
1094 fertilization are becoming common practices in recent intensive and superintensive olive
1095 orchards. Olive trees positively respond to irrigation, as many recent works have noted.

1096 Nevertheless, an appropriate strategy should be implemented because losses of minor
1097 components, particularly phenols, due to irrigation have been reported. Similarly, good
1098 control of fertilization should be performed to avoid the negative effects on olive quality
1099 (reduced firmness and decreases in the sugar and phenol contents) observed when
1100 applying excess nitrogen. Controlling pest and diseases in the olive orchard is also key to
1101 achieve high-quality products. The olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*) and Anthracnose
1102 (*Colletotrichum* spp) represent the most important sanitary problems from the point of
1103 view of quality deterioration.

1104 Finally, the harvesting timing and procedure play decisive roles in determining the final
1105 product quality. Maturity indices (MIs) are commonly used to decide when to harvest. In
1106 the case of table olives, fruits are usually picked at MI 1 for green or black-ripe
1107 processing, although the latter can be delayed until the beginning of the skin color change.
1108 Natural black olives are harvested once the fruit color has changed to black on the tree.
1109 In the case of olive oils, harvesting at MI 3 (veraison) is often recommended to ensure the
1110 maximum oil content. Nevertheless, ripening dramatically modifies the physico-chemical
1111 traits and compounds of olive fruit (see Tables 3 and 4); thus, these changes should be
1112 considered to achieve specific organoleptic and nutraceutical profiles of olive products
1113 by advancing or delaying the date of harvest. Regarding the harvesting method, manual
1114 harvesting is the best option to obtain the highest quality for both products, but it is
1115 economically inviable in most olive orchards. Mechanical harvesting is a common
1116 practice for olive oil production, but although EVOO may be obtained, decreases in
1117 certain quality attributes have been reported. In the case of table olives, the main constrain
1118 for mechanical harvesting is the high proportion of damaged fruits obtained.
1119 Nevertheless, strategies that include new machinery designs, adapting the tree canopy and
1120 post-harvest treatments will help improve the quality of mechanically harvested olives.

1121 **Conflicts of Interest**

1122 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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